
THE USE OF MEDICINAL BIOMAGNETISM FOR CHRONIC VENOUS INSUFFICIENCY – LOWER LIMBS BLOOD FLOW PROTOCOL

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ABSTRACT

The Magnetic therapies have been the focus of studies due to the positive results observed in clinical practice. The cells in the human body are affected by the application of Static Magnetic Fields (SMFs). This interaction has shown good results in the treatment of various symptoms and diseases. Based on studies of Dr. Richard Broeringmeyer, Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán developed a new therapy: Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB). One of the findings of Dr. Goiz is based on the alteration of body flows, such as vascular alteration. These allow it to be influenced by Biomagnetic Pairs (BMPs) that make it possible to sustain pathogenic microorganisms or generate tissue alterations that can hinder venous return. The Chronic Venous Insufficiency (CVI) is a deficiency of blood flow

in the deep veins of the Lower Limbs (LL), resulting from dysfunctions of venous return from the limbs to the heart, causing blood reflux, venous hypertension sustained by blood accumulation in the deep veins. MB is a non-invasive, low-cost, painless, easy-to-apply complementary practice with minimal contraindications, which aims to prevent several pathologies, including CVI, being a treatment option with great therapeutic potential. **Objective and Method:** The objective of this exploratory and qualitative bibliographic review carried out by the analytical method is to present a MB protocol that can be applied to assist in the treatment of CVI. **Results and Conclusion:** The Treatment Protocol for Lower Limb Blood Flow (LLBF) was presented as a result of this study, leading to the conclusion that it can help in the treatment of CVI, its signs and symptoms, facilitating venous return, deserving to be researched in controlled studies.

Key-Words: Medicinal Biomagnetism; Static Magnetic Field; Chronic Venous Insufficiency; Biomagnetic Pair; Venous Return; Protocol; Integrative and Complementary Practice.

1. INTRODUCTION

The natural magnetic practice has been used for more than two thousand years. It is a low-cost, non-invasive, and relatively safe therapy (LI, 2020), that uses Static Magnetic Fields (SMFs) which can be generated by magnets or by devices that carry non-variable currents (MAYROVITZ, 2022), that is, magnetic waves that induce minicurrents in the body. The effect of these currents is to correct and balance reactions of the organic systems and areas presenting dysfunctions (BROERINGMEYER, 1991).

The number of studies that discuss the applications of SMFs in the treatment of various diseases and symptoms have increased significantly, due to their applicability in the therapeutic field and the results achieved in clinical practice, showing pain relief in up to 70% of applications (MOLINARI, 2018; LI, 2020; ZHANG, 2020; BERTAGNA, 2022).

The effects of SMFs on the human body have been proven to be beneficial in treating chronic pain, tissue repair, cell proliferation and wounds, limiting edema formation and accelerating healing, affecting cells at different levels (LI, 2020; ZHANG, 2020; MAYROVITZ, 2022; BERTAGNA, 2022). In the cell membrane, the greatest interaction with the magnetic field occurs where it demonstrates to modulate the rate of ionic transport, with greater ease on displacement of ionic charges (MOLINARI, 2018; BERTAGNA, 2022).

Doctor Richard Broeringmeyer (1991), a scientific researcher who described the benefits of SMFs to the human body, observed that astronauts returning to Earth presented a shortening of the right leg. From an experiment where he applied medium-intensity magnets to the body, the asymmetric limb returned to normal alignment. He also analyzed that when applying the SMF to the body, an interaction with the bloodstream could be observed, as it contains the iron element present in hemoglobin, concluding that the field favorably affects circulation (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; CASTEJÓN, 2015).

In 1988, in a course promoted by the Guadalajara Society of Alternative Medicines in which Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán participated, Dr. Richard Broeringmeyer laid out the foundations of what he called Energy Therapy, in which the SMF combining with kinesiology could scan the body through the use of an electromagnet. Based on this technique, Dr. Goiz developed what is now known as Medicinal Biomagnetism (MB) (DURÁN, 2008).

MB is a non-invasive technique that uses SMF generated by a pair of magnets with opposite polarity, with an intensity of 1,000 to 7,500 Gauss, with the aim of neutralizing charges that are in excess. Due to the fact that the body is in pH dysfunction, by rebalancing the pH of the region that was altered, the body is then able to return to the Normal Energy Level (NEL) and thus, restore health (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; DURÁN, 2008; JIMENO, 2014; FRANK, 2017).

When there is an imbalance between positive and negative electrical charges in the body, they are concentrated in certain regions (anatomical points) and remain in magnetic resonance with each other. This concentration of energy

results in a change in the pH, which can generate dysfunctions and pathologies, forming what is known in the MB as a “Biomagnetic Pair” (BMP) (DURÁN, 2008).

The magnets used are composed of a north pole (black) and south pole (red) that generate a magnetic field and will influence the balance of the BMPs. The MB can also act in the prevention of diseases, when the distortion of the pH of the organs or tissues of the human body is corrected, which can happen even before the appearance of signs and symptoms that configure a pathology (DURÁN, 2008).

One of the findings of Dr. Goiz is based on changes in body flows, such as vascular disorders. The BMPs have influence on these flows by sustaining pathogenic microorganisms or promoting tissue variations, hindering venous return, as in the case of Chronic Venous Insufficiency (CVI) (DURÁN, 2010).

CVI is the deficiency of blood flow in the deep veins from the Lower Limbs (LL) to the heart, resulting from dysfunctions of venous return, caused by blood reflux, sustained venous hypertension and blood accumulation in the deep veins of the lower limbs (MEJÍA-GONZÁLEZ , 2022; RODAS, 2022). Lower limb CVI manifests itself in various clinical aspects, from asymptomatic problems to severe symptoms, such as venous ulcers (YOUN and LEE, 2019).

The venous system can be divided into three main components: the superficial venous system, the deep venous system and the perforating veins. The superficial venous system drains blood flow from the skin and subcutaneous tissues. Any veins located above the muscular fascia that are not deep are considered superficial veins (YOUN and LEE, 2019).

The deep venous system is responsible for approximately 90% of venous blood flow in the lower limbs. The main function of this system is to provide venous return to the heart. Perforating veins are connecting channels between the superficial and deep venous systems and play a key role in balancing blood flow during muscle contraction, preventing backflow from the deep venous system to the superficial venous system (YOUN and LEE, 2019).

The vascular reflux accumulated in the lower limbs generates increased pressure within the veins, dilating them and promoting the formation of varicose veins. With its worsening, there is the initial appearance of pain, heaviness, fatigue, edema, changes in the skin and subcutaneous tissue due to chronic venous hypertension, which can naturally progress to inflammation, eczema, lipodermatosclerosis, deep venous thrombosis and ulcers located in the lower limbs (MATIĆ, 2014; YOUN and LEE, 2019; MEJÍA-GONZÁLEZ, 2022; RODAS, 2022).

Due to the high rate of recurrence of varicose veins after the surgical procedure for their treatment, new techniques have been developed over time, such as ambulatory phlebectomy, the CHIVA method (French acronym for “Cure conservatrice et Hémodynamique de l’Insuffisance Veineuse en Ambulatoire” – Conservative and Hemodynamic treatment of Venous Insufficiency in the Office), Doppler ultrasound-guided sclerosis or the most recent ones such as Endovenous Radiofrequency Ablation (EVRFA) and endovenous laser ablation techniques, but none managed to achieve a permanently satisfactory result (RODAS, 2022).

Considering that MB is a non-invasive, low-cost, painless, easy-to-apply complementary practice with minimal contraindications, which aims at both recovery and prevention of various pathologies and dysfunctions, it is seen as a grate potential alternative to the CVI treatment (DURÁN, 2008).

The MB technique application implies the use of Complete Scanning (CS), which is the physical examination performed via kinesiological reflex. However, with the aim of facilitating clinical practice, Dr. David Goiz Martínez developed protocols for specific causes called “TOP”s, based on the BMPs that appeared most in Dr. Goiz clinical practice during the application of the technique for certain diseases and/or disorders (MARTÍNEZ, 2017a; MARTÍNEZ, 2017b; MARTÍNEZ, 2018).

The Par Magnético Institute (IPM) is a MB school in Brazil that structured the TOPs. Together with his students, based on the clinical practice of Biomagnetism therapists, it continues to develop other protocols, such as the SIS protocols

(systems protocols), the SIN protocols (symptoms protocols), the Lymphatic Protocol and the Lower Limb Blood Flow (LLBF) Treatment Protocol.

The LLBF protocol was developed by the Biomagnetism therapist Marilene Chudek Rambo based on the clinical experience of a patient with a medical diagnosis of Great Saphenous Vein Incompetence. The patient came to her with exams and reports in hand requesting assistance. After a few consultations, in a new ultrasound examination with echo Doppler, venous function had been restored without allopathic intervention. After this successful study case, the protocol was shared to be used by other Biomagnetism therapists for various venous disorders (BOSSA, 2021b; BOSSA, 2021c).

Based on the results obtained with the application of this protocol in the clinical practice of several Biomagnetism therapists, with the aim of facilitating the dissemination and use of MB to the patients, this study aims to present the Lower Limb Blood Flow Treatment Protocol – LLBF protocol (Figure 1) of the MB, in order to assist in the treatment of CVI (DURÁN, 2008).

2. METHODOLOGY

This research is a literature review of analytical method and of exploratory and qualitative character, which approaches the studied subject and converges with the proposal of presenting the MB technique protocol to aid in the treatment and improvement of lower limb blood circulation (GIL, 1991).

The following inclusion criteria were used for the selection of articles: free access articles, full text and digital object identifier (DOI). References from the MB material were used following the works of the developer of the technique, Dr. Isaac Goiz Durán and other authors who research it. Due to the lack of scientific publications in the MB area, other sources were accepted, such as books, handouts from courses in the technique and theses on this subject. The databases used in the search for articles were PubMed and SciELO, and for literature, online searches were carried out on the Google Scholar platform.

The descriptors applied to the search for articles are Static magnetic fields (SMF) + health effects, SMF + blood flow, SMF, biomagnetic field, chronic venous insufficiency, biomagnetic pair, medicinal biomagnetism, venous return, integrative and complementary practice, together with all the results of the literature found and used in this research.

Bibliographical exclusion criteria were paid articles, duplicate references, content not in line with the theme and articles without DOI.

After the selection and exploratory reading of the material found by the authors, it was possible to present the LLBF protocol for the improvement of lower limb CVI using the MB technique as presented by Bossa (2021a), as referenced in Figure 1.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After analyzing the literature available, the inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied for selection. The references used are described in Table 1.

Table 1: Result of the consulted literature

RESEARCHED THEME	PLATFORM	FILTERS	NUMBER OF SOURCES FOUND	NUMBER OF SOURCES NOT USED	NUMBER OF SOURCES USED
SMF + health effects	PubMed	5 years	9	6	3
SMF + blood flow	PubMed	5 years	11	9	2
SMF	Book	-	1	0	1
Relevant Literature	Google Scholar	-	6	0	6
Biomagnetic Pair	SciElo		1	0	1
Medicinal Biomagnetism	Books and handouts from courses	-	10	0	10
Methodology	Book	-	1	0	1
Chronic Venous insufficiency	SciElo	5 years	43	40	3
Total			82	55	27

Source: The authors.

As a practical result of this work, the MB protocol for the treatment of CVI is presented in two phases.

The first phase consists of carrying out a complete scanning (CS) protocol as systematized by Bossa (2021b), which aims to identify the particular BMPs of each patient. It is possible to treat bioelectromagnetic dysfunctions that may be related to the signs and symptoms of CVI.

In the second phase, right after the CS, the LLBF protocol is applied, as shown in Figure 1 (BOSSA, 2021a). The frequency of protocol application suggested is of at least twice a week during 40 minutes until symptoms improve.

Figure 1: Lower Limb Blood Flow (FSMI) Treatment Protocol

Caption: Protocol to improve lower limb blood flow disorders (LLBF). The convention followed for the application of magnets is used by Durán (2010) and Bossa (2021). The convention used by these MB schools describes that the application of the magnets must follow as seen in the image. When you see the red color, the black face of the magnet is placed on the skin. When you see the black color, the red face of the magnet is in contact with the skin. In the LLBF protocol, the black face of the magnets is applied along the path of the main venous return from the lower limbs. The red face of the magnets is applied to the saphenofemoral junction and the kidneys.

The LLBF protocol was designed by applying the North pole magnets (black) on the venous return path (Figure 2) and the South pole magnets (red) on the junction of the saphenous vein and femoral vein, on the lymph nodes and on both kidneys. The purpose of applying SMFs as described is due to the particular action of each of the magnetic poles.

Figure 2: Trajectory of venous return of the main veins of the lower limbs

Source: <https://www.clinicacuidarero.com.br/blog/foi-indicada-a-retirada-das-veias-safenas-e-agoraij-79&categoria=artigos>. Acesso em: 25 out. 2022

https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:2136ab_Lower_Limb_Veins_Anterior_Posterior.jpg accessed in march 2023

Through the action of the north pole of the magnet, which allows inhibiting pain, increasing alkalinity, facilitating the movement of body fluids and restricting blood vessels, among other actions, the objective is to prevent possible tissue damage and minor bleeding intensity (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; DURÁN, 2008; JIMENO, 2014; FRANK, 2017). The south pole, on the other hand, has a toning action for the tissues of the kidneys and lymph nodes, enhancing their function (BROERINGMEYER, 1991; PHILPOOT, 2000; DAVIS and RAWLS, 1974; MARTÍNEZ, 2018; DE LA CAL, 2003; MARKOV, 2014).

As demonstrated in the studies, the application of SMFs has effects such as: improvement in muscle tone, regulation of blood pressure, circulatory hemodynamics, improvement in homeostasis and baroreflex sensitivity. (LI, 2020; ZHANG, 2020; MAYROVITZ, 2022; BERTAGNA, 2022).

Although there are many procedures that are not always very effective, it is necessary to search for a new technique that is easy to apply and has low cost in order to help with the symptoms of CVI, such as the protocol proposed in this article, which will facilitate the treatment, since studies demonstrate benefits proposed by Medicinal Biomagnetism therapy with improved blood flow and vascular tone (LI, 2020; BERTAGNA, 2022).

4. CONCLUSION AND PERSPECTIVES

Based on the studied literature, a protocol that can be used as an adjuvant in the treatment of Chronic Venous Insufficiency of the lower limbs was selected and described as being capable of minimizing the signs and symptoms caused by CVI, preventing its evolution.

Considering that MB is a low-cost, non-invasive and easy-to-apply technique, treatments with SMFs have very few restrictions and demonstrate good results in clinical practice, therefore, this can be a safe protocol to be applied. However, research using the protocol is needed to prove its effectiveness, considering the existing variables in CVI care.

New research applying this treatment protocol for CVI in groups of diagnosed people using the MB technique is proposed, with the aim of demonstrating its efficiency through the evaluation of the pathological degree of CVI, considering parameters such as the duration, frequency of application and magnets that best respond to the treatment, among others.

REFERENCES

BERTAGNA, Federico; LEWIS, Rebecca; SILVA, S. Ravi P.; MCFADDEN, Johnjoe; e JEEVARATNAM, Kamalan. Thapsigargin blocks electromagnetic field elicited intracellular Ca²⁺ increase in HEK 293 cells. **Physiological Reports**, 10(9), e15189. 2022. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.14814/phy2.15189>. Accessed in: 10 oct. 2022.

BOSSA, Adriane Viapiana. **Apostila de Biomagnetismo Medicinal**. Cascavel/PR: Editora Independente; Volume 1, Ed. 12. Agosto – 2021a. Available at:

www.institutoparmagnetico.com.br. Accessed in: 10 oct. 2022.

BOSSA, Adriane Viapiana. **Protocolo de Rastreo do Biomagnetismo Medicinal**. Cascavel/PR: Editora Independente; Volume 1, Ed. 5 – 2021b. Available at: www.institutoparmagnetico.com.br. Accessed in: 27 may 2022.

BOSSA, Adriane Viapiana. **Biomagnetismo Medicinal Avanzado**. 2. ed. Cascavel: Instituto Par Magnético, 58 p., 2021c. Available at: www.institutoparmagnetico.com.br. Accessed in: 21 out. 2022.

BROERINGMEYER, Richard. **Principios de la Terapia Magnetica/Bio-magnetismo**. Health Industries, Inc, 1991.

CASTEJÓN, Enrique de Juan Gonzalez, **Efectos Biológicos de la Terapia del Par Biomagnético**, Tesis Doctoral, Alcalá de Henares, 2015.

DAVIS, Albert Roy. **La Anatomia del Biomagnetismo**. Volumen 3, No. 61874.

DAVIS, Albert Roy e RAWLS Jr, Walter C. **Magnetism and its effects on the living system**. Smithtown, NY. An Exposition-University Book, Exposition Press, 1974.

DE LA CAL, Antonio Madroñero. Utilización terapéutica de los campos magnéticos. I: Fundamentos del biomagnetismo. Patología del Aparato Locomotor, 2004; 2 (1): 22-37.

DURÁN, Isaac Goiz. **El Par Biomagnético**. 5. ed. Chapingo, México D. F.: Universidad Autónoma Chapingo, 171 p., 2008.

DURÁN, Isaac Goiz; MARTINEZ, Xabier Zabala; CASTELAN, Guillermo Mendoza, **El Código Patógeno**, Universidad Autonoma Chapingo, 2010.

FRANK, Bryan L. Biomagnetic Pair Therapy and Typhoid Fever: A Pilot Study. **Medical Acupuncture**, [S.L.], v. 29, n. 5, p. 308-312, out. 2017. Mary Ann Liebert Inc. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC5653337/>. Accessed in: 27 May 2022.

GIL, Antônio Carlos. **Como elaborar projetos de pesquisa**. São Paulo: Atlas, 1991.

JIMENO, Rosel Ucles; PENA, María del Pilar Amaro; BAENA, Marina Domingo. Evolución de la glucosa en pacientes geriátricos diabéticos con la aplicación del par biomagnético. **Gerokomos**, Barcelona, v. 25, n. 3, p. 107-110, sept. 2014. Available at <https://dx.doi.org/10.4321/S1134-928X2014000300005>. Accessed in 25 July 2022.

LI, Qin; LIAO, Zhongcai; GU, Lili; ZHANG, Lei; ZHANG, Lingxi; TIAN, Xiaofei; LI, Jun; FANG, Zhicai e ZHANG, Xinyue. Moderate Intensity Static Magnetic Fields Prevent Thrombus Formation in Rats and Mice. **Bioelectromagnetics**, 47 (1), 52-62. 2020. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bem.22232>. Accessed in: Nov 3rd 2022.

MARKOV, Marko. S. Electromagnetic Fields and Life. **Journal of Electrical & Electronic Systems** 2014, 3:1. Disponível em <https://www.hilarispublisher.com/open-access/electromagnetic-fields-and-life-2332-0796-3-119.pdf>. Accessed in: Aug. 10th, 2022.

MARTÍNEZ, David Goiz. **Guía de Pares Biomagnéticos primer nivel**. Ciudad de México: Biomagnetism Research Institute, 142 p., 2017a.

MARTÍNEZ, David Goiz. **Guía de Pares Biomagnéticos segundo nivel**. Ciudad de México: Biomagnetism Research Institute, 120 p., 2017b.

MARTÍNEZ, David Goiz. **Manual del biomagnetista**. Ciudad de México: Biomagnetism Research Institute, 169 p., 2018.

MATIĆ, Predrag A.; VLAJINAC, Hristina D.; MARINKOVIĆ, Jelena M.; MAKSIMOVIĆ, Milos Ž. e RADAK, Đorđe. J. Chronic venous disease: Correlation between ultrasound findings and the clinical, etiologic, anatomic and pathophysiologic classification. **Phlebology: The Journal of Venous Disease**, 29(8), 522-527. 2014 Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0268355513497360>. Accessed in Oct. 3rd, 2022.

MAYROVITZ, Harvey N.; MAQSOOD, Raneem e TAWAKALZADA, Aneil S. Do Magnetic Fields Have a Place in Treating Vascular Complications in Diabetes?

Cureus, 14 (5), e24883. 2022. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.24883>.

Accessed in July 20th 2022.

MEJÍA-GONZÁLEZ, Madiam; LÓPEZ-VILLA-ENTEBI, Enrique; CHÁVEZ-VALENCIA, Venice e CHÁVEZ-SAAVEDRA, Vladimir J. Prevalencia de enfermedad venosa crónica en personal de salud y su impacto en calidad de vida a 6 meses. **Cirugia y cirujanos**, 90 (3), 332–337. 2022 <https://doi.org/10.24875/CIRU.20001245>.

Accessed in Oct. 5th, 2022.

MOLINARI, Claudio; STOPPA, Ian; LIMARDO, Nicola e UBERTI, Francesca (2018). Evaluation of the Effectiveness of Protective Patches on Acupoints to Preserve the Bioenergetic Status against Magnetic Fields. **Evidence-Based Complementary and Alternative Medicine: eCAM**, 2018, 4732130.

<https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/4732130>. Accessed in Oct. 18th, 2022.

PHILPOTT, William H.; KALITA, Dwight K; GOLDBERG, Burton. **Magnet therapy: an alternative medicine definitive guide** Tiburon, Ca: AlternativeMedicine.com Books, 2000 https://archive.org/details/isbn_9781887299213/page/n2/mode/2up.

Accessed in Oct. 3rd 2022.

RODAS, Jorge; ROA, Gustavo; PORTILLO, Gloria; AGUILERA, Panambi; LEZCANO, Roberto e VERDECCHIA, Chynthia. Manejo, diagnóstico y tratamiento de la insuficiencia venosa de miembros inferiores. Hospital Militar Central. Período 2017 – 2021. **Cirugía paraguaya. Cir. paragrafo, Assunción**, v. 46, n. 1. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.18004/sopaci.2022.abril.7>. Accessed in April 19th 2022.

YOUN, Young Jin e LEE, JuYong. Chronic venous insufficiency and varicose veins of the lower extremities. **KJIM – The Korean Journal of Internal Medicine** Vol. 34 (2), Korean J Intern Med 2019;34:269-283 2019

<https://doi.org/10.3904/kjim.2018.230>. Accessed in Oct. 5th, 2022.

ZHANG, Bin; XIE, Yangli; NI, Zhenhong e CHEN, Lin. Effects and Mechanisms of Exogenous Electromagnetic Field on Bone Cells: A Review.

Bioelectromagnetics, 41 (4), 263-278. 2020. Available at:

<https://doi.org/10.1002/bem.22258>. Accessed in Set 12th 2022.

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